

DEFINITIONS OF TECHNOLOGY AND TECHNOLOGY INTEGRATION

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Abstract:

This thesis provides the definitions of technology and technology integration which were said by famous scholars.

Key words: technology, integration, classroom activities, language acquisition, language skills, assignments

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Introduction

In and out of the classroom, the use of technology has become an integral aspect of the learning process. Almost every language lesson makes use of technology in some way. Language has been helped and improved by the use of technology learning. Teachers can adjust classroom activities thanks to technology, they improve the process of language acquisition. Technology advances at a rapid pace as a tool to assist teachers in facilitating language learning for their learners.

Main part

Language is one of the significant elements that affects international communication activities. Students utilize different parts of English language skills such as listening, speaking, reading, and writing for their proficiency and communication (Grabe& Stoller, 2002). In addition, Ahmadi (2017) stated that one of the important elements for learning is the method that instructors use in their classes to facilitate language learning process. According to Becker (2000), computers are regarded as an important instructional instrument in language classes in which teachers have convenient access, are sufficiently prepared, and have some freedom in the curriculum. Computer technology is regarded by a lot of teachers to be a significant part of providing a high -quality education.

According to Bull and Ma (2001), technology provides offers unlimited resources to language learners. Harmer (2007) and Gençlter (2015) emphasized and teachers should encourage learners to find appropriate activities through using computer technology in order to be successful in language learning.

Technology has always been an important part of teaching and learning environment. It is an essential part of the teachers' profession through which they can use it to facilitate learners' learning. When we talk about technology in teaching and learning, the word 'integration' is used. With technology being part of our everyday lives, it is time to rethink the idea of integrating technology into the curriculum and aim to embed technology into teaching to support the learning process. That is to say, technology becomes an integral part of the learning experience and a significant issue for teachers, from the beginning of

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preparing learning experiences through to teaching and learning process (Eady& Lockyer, 2013).

Solanki and Shyamlee1 (2012) and Pourhosein Gilakjani (2017) supported the view that language teaching method has been changed due to technology. The researchers continued that the application of technology helps learners learn on the basis of their interests. It also satisfies both visual and auditory senses of the learners. According to Lam and Lawrence (2002), technology assists learners in adjusting their own learning process and they can have access to a lot of information that their teachers are not able to provide.

Technology has been defined by different researchers. According to İŞMAN (2012), it is the practical use of knowledge particularly in a specific area and is a way of doing a task especially using technical processes, methods, or knowledge. The usage of technology includes not only machines (computer hardware) and instruments, but also involves structured relations with other humans, machines, and the environment (İŞMAN, 2012).

According to Hennessy, Ruthven, and Brindley (2005), technology integration is defined in terms of how teachers use technology to perform familiar activities more effectively and how this usage can re -shape these activities. Dockstader (2008) defined technology integration as the use of technology to improve the educational environment. It supports the classroom teaching through creating opportunities for learners to complete assignments on the computer rather than the normal pencil and paper.

Furthermore, Tomlison (2009) say that computer -based activities provide learners rapid information and appropriate materials. They continue that internet materials motivate learners to learn more [35]. In addition, Larsen - Freeman and Anderson (2011) supported the view that technology provides teaching resources and brings learning experience to the learners' world. Through using technology, many authentic materials can be provided to learners and they can be motivated in learning language.

Dawson, Cavanaugh, and Ritzhaupt (2008) maintained that using technology can create a learning atmosphere centered around the learner rather than the teacher that in turn creates positive changes. They emphasized that by using computer technology, language class becomes an active place full of meaningful tasks where the learners are responsible for their learning. Drayton, Falk, Stroud, Hobbs, and Hammerman (2010) argued that using computer technology indicates a true learning experience that enhances learners' responsibilities. Technology encourages learners to learn individually and to acquire responsible behaviors. The independent use of technologies gives learners self-direction.

Conclusion

To sum up, technology is becoming more prevalent in education around the world, and it is having an increasingly significant impact on the design and delivery of language learning programs. Today's language teachers are required to know how to incorporate technology into their classrooms, as well as how to help students use media and the internet to boost their learning of all four skills. As a result, technology presents both new challenges and opportunities for both teachers and students.

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